

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN COLORS AND THEIR SYMBOLIC MEANING IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

Turaeva Guzal Khudoy nazarovna

Senior teacher

Termez State University

guzalya1977@mail.ru

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Abstract: Color designation is an important part of language and culture. Colors can have different meanings and symbolic meanings in different cultures and languages. This article examines color designation in Uzbek and English in languages, analyzes key words and their symbolic meaning.

Key words: color designation, language, symbolic meaning, culture

Language is not only a means of communication, but also a way of expressing the cultural characteristics and traditions of different peoples. Colors play an important role in language; their meaning can have deep symbolic meaning. Studying color terms in different languages allows us to better understand the culture of each people.

Color is of great importance in a person's life. In different cultures, the symbolism of the same colors is different. As a rule, each color evokes certain sensations and is associated with something. But, every nation has its own ideas about the meaning of one color or another. Almost all nations have noticed the convenience of using color as a symbol. But, based on different environments and conditions of existence, the same color is associated with different phenomena among different peoples.

Let's look at the symbolism of color in different cultures. White was already noted and isolated as a special color in ancient times. S.G. Ter Minasova notes that the ancient symbolic meanings of white are mostly positive: white means joy, harmony, peace, purity, health. In addition, white color is the joy of the spirit, innocence, purity [Ter-Minasova, 2000]. According to A.V. Kunin, in European culture, the semantics of white has a more negative meaning, namely death, hunger, silence, loneliness [Kunin, 2006].

Colors that differ from each other only in lightness are called achromatic (colorless). These include: white, gray, black. The remaining colors are chromatic (color), which can be divided into warm (long-wavelength part of the spectrum: red, orange, yellow, yellow-green) and cold (short-wavelength part of the spectrum: green-blue, cyan, green, indigo, violet). Pure green lies between the cool and warm colors of the spectrum. From the point of view of physics, colors are also divided into primary (yellow, blue, red), from which all other colors can theoretically be composed, and mixed (green, purple, orange, brown, blue) [3, p. 65].

The combination of these colors characterizes such a phenomenon as color space, which is purely psychological, since in nature there are only light waves, the length of which varies in a certain range, and the color itself is the result of the activity of the brain and eye. Categorization of the linguistic color space occurs through color terms.

In the Uzbek language, colors are used not only to represent objects, but also to convey emotions and mood. For example, the word "qizil" (red) can mean not only the color itself, but also love and passion. Also in the Uzbek language there are color idioms that are used in

everyday speech and literary works. For example, the expression " oq dunyo " (white peace) means peace and harmony.

The English language also has its own peculiarities in color designation. The English language is characterized by the traditional association of black with something bad. Therefore, phrases with the adjective " black " have negative connotations, for example, " black market " – "black market"; « black armband " - "black armband." There are also expressions and idioms in English that use colors. For example, " green with envy " (green with envy) and " blue blood "(blue blood).

As for the English word " red ", it is used in the language not only in the meaning of "red", but is also used to describe animal fur and human hair in the meaning of "red": " red – haired " - "red-haired", " red" fox - "red fox".

Color designations in Uzbek and English have different features and symbolic meanings. Analyzing colors and their use in the Uzbek and English languages allows us to better understand these cultures and the transmission of emotional content in languages. Learning about color is an important part of cultural diversity and intercultural exchange.

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